

EVALUATION OF CORRELATION BETWEEN IMPACT-INDUCED CRACK GROWTH BEHAVIOR AND INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS IN CFRP LAMINATES

Yasuhiro KOICHI*¹, Hiroshi SAITO², Isao KIMPARA³

¹Graduate Student, Kanazawa Institute of Technology,
7-1 Ohgigaoka, Nonoichi, Ishikawa, Japan
Email: b1040368@planrt.kanazawa-it.ac.jp

²College of Engineering, Kanazawa Institute of Technology,
3-1 Yatukaho, Hakusan, Ishikawa, Japan
Email: saito@neptune.kanazawa-it.ac.jp, web page: <http://www2.kanazawa-it.ac.jp/compos/top.html>

³Research Laboratory for Integrated Technological Systems, Kanazawa Institute of Technology,
3-1 Yatukaho, Hakusan, Ishikawa, Japan

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ABSTRACT

The elucidation of the failure mechanisms are essential for prediction of CAI strength of structural FRP based on numerical simulations. Especially, propagation behavior of impact-induced damages, such as transverse crack and delamination, should be verified by comparing with experimental observation results, in which clarification of a certain “mapping” of dominant fracture mode is included. Precise observation, mainly focused on the crack and delamination, is necessary at a cross-section of FRP after impact.

In this study, at first, we precisely observed cross-sections of CFRP laminates after impact. Transverse cracks and delaminations are focused as our main targets to classify the dominant fracture mode observed in the impact-induced damage. In the next step, a numerical simulation is conducted by using experimental data such as mode I and mode II fracture toughness in order to verify the distribution and the mechanism of dominant fracture mode observed in experiments. Finally, we identified consistency between mapping of fracture mode and the result of numerical simulation. Compared mapping of fracture mode and the result of numerical simulation, impact damages in CFRP laminate propagates delamination of fracture mode II by increasing shearing deformation after resin crack and transverse crack by tension becomes the starting point. It is thought that mapping of fracture mode and numerical simulation results have consistency.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP), which have higher specific rigidity and strength than metals, such as steels and aluminium alloy, have been used as the structural materials in warplane and the helicopter, car, sporting goods and so on. However, it is necessary to validate higher safety when CFRP spreads as structural materials more widely [1-3]. Fracture mechanism, especially impact damage, is quite complicated in FRP. Typical damages caused by impact are delamination, transverse crack, matrix crack and fiber fracture [1,4-5]. In particular, delamination causes significant degradation of compressive strength of laminated FRP [6-8]. Thus, interlaminar fracture toughness, which is an index of difficulty of causing delamination, is one of the most important design parameters as well as compressive strength after impact (CAI strength) [4-9].

The elucidation of the failure mechanisms are essential for prediction of CAI strength of structural FRP based on numerical simulations. Especially, propagation behavior of impact-induced damages, such as transverse crack and delamination, should be verified by comparing with experimental observation results, in which clarification of a certain “mapping” of dominant fracture mode is

included. If we can obtain such “mapping” of dominant fracture mode, it can be also applied to the material design, for example, to prevent particular fracture mode. Thus, precise observation, mainly focused on the crack and delamination, is necessary at a cross-section of FRP after impact.

In this study, at first, we precisely observed cross-sections of CFRP laminates after impact. Transverse cracks and delaminations are focused as our main targets to classify the dominant fracture mode observed in the impact-induced damage. Impact damage was applied to CFRP laminates by using drop-weight impact machine. Cross-sectional observation was conducted by optical microscope in order to observe damage morphology. In the next step, a numerical simulation is conducted by using experimental data such as mode I and mode II fracture toughness in order to verify the distribution and the mechanism of dominant fracture mode observed in experiments. Finally, we identified consistency between mapping of fracture mode and the result of numerical simulation.

2 MATERIALS AND SPECIMEN

CFRP laminate used in this study were made from T700/#2592 prepreg (Toray Industries, Inc.) Stacking sequence was $[0/90]_{3s}$. Dimension of specimen is shown in Fig.1. Length of specimen is 150[mm] and width is 50[mm], thickness is 3[mm].

Fig.1 Dimension of specimen

3 IMPACT TEST

Drop-weight impact testing machine is shown in Fig.2. Specimens were held with two steel plate fixtures which have cutout hole of 30[mm] in diameter. Weight of impactor was 0.998[kg] and diameter of impactor was 16[mm]. The impact energy applied to specimens was 1.25[J/mm].

Fig.2 Drop-weight impact testing machine

4 ULTRASONIC INSPECTION

Inside damage of specimen after impact test was observed by the ultrasonic scanning device with 5[MHz] probe (TU-2000, Toray Engineering Co., Ltd.). Ultrasonic scanning image of impact damages is shown in Fig.3. In this figure, delamination spreads through the fiber direction from the central impact point.

Fig.3 Ultrasonic inspection image of CFRP specimen after impact test

5 CROSS-SECTIONAL OBSERVATION

To observe the cross section of specimen after impact test, specimens was cut in 30[mm] in the perpendicular direction of fiber direction and 20[mm] in the direction appeared on the surface of specimen fiber direction. Cut specimen was mounted in resin and its surface was polished to mirror finish.

The optical microscope (VHX-500, Keyence Co., Ltd.), shown in Fig.4, was used for the cross-sectional observation after impact. Figure 5 shows the cross-section right side of impact point. In this figure, position of yellow circles indicate transverse crack, blue circles shows delamination and red circles shows resin crack.

Figure.6 shows a typical transverse crack observed in Fig.5. It is obvious that transverse cracks occur along the interface between fibers and resin. Thus, it is supposed that these transverse cracks originate from the interfacial fracture caused by tension.

Figures.7 and 8 show typical cross-sectional photographs of impact-induced resin crack and delamination. Hackle-like fracture mode was observed at the surface of delamination. According to study of Greenhalghes [10], tensile stress occurs in direction that is perpendicular to fiber axis in stress field of crack front. Based on this factor, in this stress field, principal stress caused by shear deformation acts in 45-degree against in-plane direction, and tensile failure occurred in matrix resin (Fig. 9(a)). According to increasing of deformation, these cracks are connected each other, and typical hackle-like fracture morphology was appeared (Fig. 9(b)). Thus, it is proven that dominant fracture mode in delaminations caused by impact is mode II [11-12].

Figure.10 shows mapping of dominant fracture mode. In this figure, dotted lines indicate impact point, red lines show mode-II-type delaminations and blue lines show cracks caused by tension. It seems that mode-II-type delaminations occur originated from transverse cracks. We discuss the failure mechanisms of impact later in the numerical simulation.

Fig.4 Optical microscope

Impact
↓

Fig.5 Cross-sectional photographs of CFRP after impact

Fig.6 Transverse crack

Fig.7 Resin crack

Fig.8 Delamination

Fig.9 Schematic illustrations of stress field

Fig.10 Mapping of fracture modes observed adjacent to the impact point

6 ANALYTICAL VERIFICATION OF FAILURE LOCATION AND FRACTURE MODE BASED ON FEM

Finite element analysis was used to investigate stress distribution in the impact test. In this study, we adopted a static push model, which simulated the quasi-static drop-weight test. The aim of this analysis is to know the location where initial failure occurs. Therefore, we conducted static elastic analyses, not dynamic failure propagation analyses. The result of analysis was compared with experimental observation in order to elucidate the distribution and the mechanism of dominant fracture mode caused by impact damage. Finally, we identified consistency between mapping of fracture mode and the result of numerical simulation. Numerical simulation was conducted by using MSC. Mentat 2013.1 as a commercialized pre-post software and MSC. Marc 2013.1 as a solver.

6.1 DISTRIBUTION OF TENSILE STRESS IN EACH LAYER

Figure.11 shows the distribution of tensile stress in the in-plane perpendicular direction of each layer. Element type is 8-node three-dimensional isoparametric solid element. The numbers of nodes and elements were 29,449 and 26,496, respectively. Tensile strength in 90-degree direction was 81.1[MPa], which is referred from a literature [13]. In this figure, the location reached the tensile strength of 90° layer was just right-side and back-side of loading point. Comparing Fig.11 with Fig.10, higher stress

can be observed at the point where transverse cracks penetrated each layer, and mode II-type failure occurred in neighborhood of these tensile failures.

It is supposed that the location where transverse cracks occurred correspond with the inflection point of specimen, where suffers only tensile stress, as shown in Fig.12. Then, mode-II-type delaminations propagated originated from transverse cracks.

Fig.11 Distribution of in-plane tensile stress in 90° direction calculated by FEM

Fig.12 Schematic illustration of mechanism of transverse crack

6.2 DISTRIBUTION OF INTERLAMINAR SHEAR STRESS OF FIBER DIRECTION 0 DEGREES

Figure.13 shows distribution of interlaminar shear stress in-plane direction of each layer. Interlaminar shear strength in 0-degree direction was 116[MPa], which is referred from a literature [13]. In this figure, the location reached the interlaminar shear strength of 0° layer was just right-side and back-side of loading point. Comparing Fig.13 with Fig.11, the initial tensile failure occurred when the deflection reached 0.084 mm, whereas the initial shear failure occurred at 0.114 mm. Therefore, in the impact-induced damage, it is estimated that transverse cracks occur followed by mode-II-type delaminations.

Here, in our previous trial [12], impact-induced damage of CFRP laminate is elucidated experimentally by high-speed in situ observation. According to this study, transverse cracks occurred followed by propagation of delaminations originated from the tips of transverse cracks. Photographs of observed failure process are shown in Fig.14.

From these references, it can be said that the tendency of result of numerical simulation shows good consistency with realistic impact-induced damage mechanism.

Fig.13 Distribution of in-plane interlaminar shear stress in 0° direction calculated by FEM

Fig.14 Propagation of delaminations originated from the tips of transverse cracks

7 CONCLUSIONS

We performed drop-weight impact test and cross-sectional observation after impact test of CFRP laminate to know detailed fracture mechanism of impact damage to be necessary for prediction of CAI strength. By cross-sectional observation and mapping of dominant fracture mode, it seems that mode-II-type delaminations occur originated from transverse cracks. Compared mapping of fracture mode provided by observation with numerical simulation result, we investigated their consistency. As this result, in the impact-induced damage, it is estimated that transverse cracks occur followed by mode-II-type delaminations. According to our previous trial, transverse cracks occurred followed by propagation of delaminations originated from the tips of transverse cracks.

From these references, it can be said that the tendency of result of numerical simulation shows good consistency with realistic impact-induced damage mechanism.

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